

**02 INFORMATION ABOUT PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS/PROJECT DIRECTORS(PI/PD) and
co-PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS/co-PROJECT DIRECTORS**

Submit only ONE copy of this form for each PI/PD and co-PI/PD identified on the proposal. The form(s) should be attached to the original proposal as specified in GPG Section II.B. Submission of this information is voluntary and is not a precondition of award. This information will not be disclosed to external peer reviewers. **DO NOT INCLUDE THIS FORM WITH ANY OF THE OTHER COPIES OF YOUR PROPOSAL AS THIS MAY COMPROMISE THE CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE INFORMATION.**

PI/PD Name: Wendy K Warnick

Gender: Male Female
Ethnicity: (Choose one response) Hispanic or Latino Not Hispanic or Latino

Race:
(Select one or more)
 American Indian or Alaska Native
 Asian
 Black or African American
 Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
 White

Disability Status:
(Select one or more)
 Hearing Impairment
 Visual Impairment
 Mobility/Orthopedic Impairment
 Other
 None

Citizenship: (Choose one) U.S. Citizen Permanent Resident Other non-U.S. Citizen

Check here if you do not wish to provide any or all of the above information (excluding PI/PD name):

REQUIRED: Check here if you are currently serving (or have previously served) as a PI, co-PI or PD on any federally funded project

Ethnicity Definition:

Hispanic or Latino. A person of Mexican, Puerto Rican, Cuban, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin, regardless of race.

Race Definitions:

American Indian or Alaska Native. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of North and South America (including Central America), and who maintains tribal affiliation or community attachment.

Asian. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of the Far East, Southeast Asia, or the Indian subcontinent including, for example, Cambodia, China, India, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippine Islands, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Black or African American. A person having origins in any of the black racial groups of Africa.

Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Hawaii, Guam, Samoa, or other Pacific Islands.

White. A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Europe, the Middle East, or North Africa.

WHY THIS INFORMATION IS BEING REQUESTED:

The Federal Government has a continuing commitment to monitor the operation of its review and award processes to identify and address any inequities based on gender, race, ethnicity, or disability of its proposed PIs/PDs. To gather information needed for this important task, the proposer should submit a single copy of this form for each identified PI/PD with each proposal. Submission of the requested information is voluntary and will not affect the organization's eligibility for an award. However, information not submitted will seriously undermine the statistical validity, and therefore the usefulness, of information received from others. Any individual not wishing to submit some or all the information should check the box provided for this purpose. (The exceptions are the PI/PD name and the information about prior Federal support, the last question above.)

Collection of this information is authorized by the NSF Act of 1950, as amended, 42 U.S.C. 1861, et seq. Demographic data allows NSF to gauge whether our programs and other opportunities in science and technology are fairly reaching and benefiting everyone regardless of demographic category; to ensure that those in under-represented groups have the same knowledge of and access to programs and other research and educational opportunities; and to assess involvement of international investigators in work supported by NSF. The information may be disclosed to government contractors, experts, volunteers and researchers to complete assigned work; and to other government agencies in order to coordinate and assess programs. The information may be added to the Reviewer file and used to select potential candidates to serve as peer reviewers or advisory committee members. See Systems of Records, NSF-50, "Principal Investigator/Proposal File and Associated Records", 63 Federal Register 267 (January 5, 1998), and NSF-51, "Reviewer/Proposal File and Associated Records", 63 Federal Register 268 (January 5, 1998).

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CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 04-23. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix C of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix D of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Jan 24 2006 8:21PM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

PROJECT SUMMARY: ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE U.S. ARCTIC SCIENCE PROGRAM, 2006–2011

The Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS) proposes to the National Science Foundation (NSF) Office of Polar Programs (OPP) a five-year cooperative agreement to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Arctic Sciences Section to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education. Building on its major accomplishments, ARCUS will continue to serve the goals of the NSF arctic programs through tasks that cannot be accomplished as effectively by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or by currently existing advisory bodies. ARCUS proposes to carry out a range of activities organized within four main tasks:

1. Arctic Science Planning - coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries;
2. Arctic Sciences Section Coordination - specific coordination and support for the OPP Arctic Sciences Section programs;
3. Arctic Science Education - development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
4. Information and Outreach - information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and the public.

Through these activities, the proposed work will:

- increase communication and coordination among researchers, projects, institutions, and agencies;
- inform policy makers, funding agencies, educators, and the public on the needs, opportunities, and benefits in arctic research; and
- improve offerings and programs in science education.

Intellectual Merit

The proposed work will advance knowledge and understanding of the Arctic across the physical, natural, and social domains through science planning activities that facilitate an integrated and interdisciplinary approach to arctic research. Through synthesizing scientific information from many sources, ARCUS provides the means for researchers to translate broad scientific goals into specific implementation plans and to integrate and disseminate their research efforts effectively. With over 15 years of experience and outstanding prior work, ARCUS is well qualified

to conduct the project and has excellent human, administrative, and technical resources.

Broader Impacts

The broader impacts resulting from the proposed activities are significant:

Integrating Research and Education: The proposed Arctic Science Education activities, including teacher research experience and visiting speaker programs, are designed to bridge research and education in accordance with guiding principles in science education. In addition, arctic research informational materials developed through science coordination activities provide valuable learning resources for scientists, educators, and the public.

Broadening Participation of Under-Represented Groups: All proposed activities employ methods to engage a broad and diverse community. Strategic efforts in selection of workshop participants and committees, development and review of publications, and use of Internet communications technologies will ensure participation of a wide variety of groups, including those under-represented due to geographic isolation or those lacking a well-developed support infrastructure.

Enhancing Infrastructure for Research and Education by Building Networks and Partnerships: The proposed work enhances infrastructure for research and education through developing networks and supporting partnerships among research institutions, individual researchers, educators, students, and arctic communities. The proposed activities will bring these groups together to discuss shared issues, resulting in a greater understanding of the Arctic and its impact on the broader global issues.

Broad Dissemination: Broad dissemination of information and resources on arctic research is an integral and explicit part of every proposed task. Through electronic media, website activities, and mailings, arctic research resources will be disseminated to thousands of researchers, educators, policy makers, and the public across the globe.

Benefits to Society: The proposed work will significantly improve communication, integration, and coordination of arctic research and education efforts, thus improving decision-making concerning the Arctic—a region undergoing profound change and an integral part of the global natural and social systems.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

For font size and page formatting specifications, see GPG section II.C.

	Total No. of Pages	Page No.* (Optional)*
Cover Sheet for Proposal to the National Science Foundation		
Project Summary (not to exceed 1 page)	1	_____
Table of Contents	1	_____
Project Description (Including Results from Prior NSF Support) (not to exceed 15 pages) (Exceed only if allowed by a specific program announcement/solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	15	_____
References Cited	2	_____
Biographical Sketches (Not to exceed 2 pages each)	4	_____
Budget (Plus up to 3 pages of budget justification)	22	_____
Current and Pending Support	4	_____
Facilities, Equipment and Other Resources	2	_____
Special Information/Supplementary Documentation	2	_____
Appendix (List below.) (Include only if allowed by a specific program announcement/ solicitation or if approved in advance by the appropriate NSF Assistant Director or designee)	_____	_____
Appendix Items:		

*Proposers may select any numbering mechanism for the proposal. The entire proposal however, must be paginated. Complete both columns only if the proposal is numbered consecutively.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE U.S. ARCTIC SCIENCE PROGRAM, 2006–2011

The significance of arctic research is growing rapidly as accumulating evidence indicates that the Arctic and its residents are vulnerable to environmental, social, and economic changes and that arctic climate and ecosystems are changing substantially (Serreze et al. 2000, ACIA 2005, Hansen et al. 2006). Climate models demonstrate both that the arctic environment will react particularly sensitively to global climate change and that changes in the Arctic will have major effects on the global climate system (Manabe and Stouffer 1994, IPCC 2001). The observed changes, and the processes that cause them, appear to be linked to the whole Northern Hemisphere, involving physical characteristics in the atmosphere, ocean, and on land (Moritz et al. 2002). Both scientists and arctic residents report ecosystem changes (Sturm et al. 2001, Krupnik and Jolly 2002). Rapid social changes also are taking place in the Arctic. From relative self-sufficiency in the recent past, arctic peoples now are incorporated into national states and the global economy, and in many instances face massive social, political, and economic changes (Chapin et al. 2004).

To address these and other interrelated phenomena, research in the Arctic increasingly takes an integrated, interdisciplinary approach (IARPC 2005) as investigators seek to understand the full context of their studies and wider implications of their results.

Funded by a variety of local, federal, and international agencies, arctic researchers examine a vast range of issues, from physical processes to ecological dynamics to institutional politics.

Arctic research topics require investigations on land, sea, ice, and air, in every season, in international waters, and in all the countries of the circumpolar north (USARC 2005, IARPC 1987–2005), and projects increasingly encompass the circumarctic region as a whole, stimulating international collaborations (IASC 2005) to compare results from

Small icebergs float near Thule, Greenland. Photo by John Sode, teacher participant in the 2005 Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating program.

different locations. This broad approach poses major challenges to existing academic and funding structures that developed largely to support single investigators working within one academic discipline (Metzger and Zare 1999, The National Academies 2004). Planning and implementing arctic research requires a dedicated effort to plan and coordinate research programs, to inform and involve the scientific community, and to integrate and synthesize the results of many investigators. The Arctic Research Policy Act of 1984 recognized this need, designating the National Science Foundation as the lead federal agency for arctic research.

The Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS) serves the diverse research community and provides the means for arctic researchers to translate broad scientific goals into specific and detailed implementation plans and to integrate and disseminate their research efforts effectively. ARCUS provides essential organizational support for the development of efficiently managed arctic research programs by:

- facilitating the identification of interdisciplinary research priorities,
- bringing these research opportunities to the attention of relevant funding sources,
- providing information and assistance for the dissemination of research results and integration across programs, and
- advocating for arctic research support in appropriate policy circles.

ABOUT ARCUS

ARCUS is a non-profit membership corporation currently consisting of 47 institutions that are organized and operated for educational, professional, and scientific purposes. Educational and research institutions established the consortium in 1988, with the support and encouragement of several federal agencies, including the National Science Foundation, to strengthen and advance arctic research to meet national needs. Based in the scientific community, the ARCUS organizational structure supports planning and implementation of initiatives and programs that benefit the general accumulation of knowledge,

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: INTRODUCTION

research institutions, individual researchers, and arctic communities. A 13-member Board of Directors, nominated by the arctic research and education community, governs ARCUS. The Council of ARCUS, consisting of an authorized representative from each member institution, elects the Board of Directors except for the President, who is elected by the board itself. The Council meets annually to conduct corporate business and to host the *Arctic Forum* (see page C-7). The Board of Directors and Council further the mission of ARCUS by broadening the participation and support of the arctic research community in ARCUS activities.

The Executive Director, Wendy Warnick, manages the programs and activities of ARCUS—assisting the development and implementation of science plans and education programs, orchestrating advocacy and information efforts, and coordinating scientific workshops and conferences. Wendy has served ARCUS for over 14 years and has an excellent understanding of the scientific, monetary, and logistical issues facing arctic researchers. She has worked closely with over 45 boards, working groups, and advisory committees; countless individual researchers; and dozens of agency personnel. She directs a closely knit staff of exceptionally competent and technologically savvy professionals. Especially skilled in synthesizing and integrating scientific information from many sources and using a variety of ways to present it both accurately and comprehensibly to diverse audiences, the ARCUS staff has organized over 65 meetings and workshops, arranged travel and processed expense reports for approximately 2,500 participants, and published over 3,500 pages of

concise, coherent, and synthesized proceedings and recommendations. Increasingly, the staff employ web-based communications tools to support committees and working groups and to reduce travel, which is meeting with a very positive response from the research community. ARCUS has an established record of sound fiscal and administrative systems.

Among the organizations involved in arctic research and engineering, the role of ARCUS is unique. ARCUS seeks to assist the implementation of arctic research in the most productive—and efficient—manner possible, by supporting, enhancing, and extending the capabilities of the scientific community. ARCUS serves the community by taking on those tasks needed for the orderly growth of arctic research that cannot be accomplished in isolation by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or other advisory bodies. With the sponsorship of relevant agencies, ARCUS draws on and works with the academic community and funding agencies, providing community leadership by:

- convening science planning committees and working groups to develop and focus program recommendations and to suggest appropriate implementation strategies,
- organizing efforts to address various science, policy, and advocacy concerns, and
- fostering the transfer of knowledge nationally and internationally.

In all its activities, ARCUS emphasizes the importance of disseminating research results and resources to the scientific community, arctic communities, and the public. ARCUS provides a key communication link among investigators, institutions, providers of information and logistical support, and funding agencies through an extensive website with links to member organizations and research projects, databases, other electronic media, a newsletter, community contacts, and member representatives. ARCUS has demonstrated that an organization with roots in the academic sector can effectively assist the federal agencies that support or conduct arctic research by promoting and managing these research opportunities and their challenges. ARCUS has an excellent track record in coordinating interdisciplinary science planning and in promoting and organizing important research and education efforts to advance knowledge and understanding of the Arctic across the physical, natural, and social domains.

A group of ARCUS staff members model TREC t-shirts outside the office in Fairbanks, Alaska.

RESULTS OF PRIOR SUPPORT

ARCUS has received support from NSF for the past 14 years under the following awards titled *Organizational Support to the U.S.*

Arctic Science Program:

- OPP-0101279: 04/01–03/06 - \$9,668,638
- OPP-9727899: 01/98–03/01 - \$3,052,331
- OPP-9404321: 05/94–04/98 - \$1,655,495
- DPP-9210133: 10/92–12/93 - \$544,305

Other NSF grants include:

- GEO-0122083: 10/01–09/03 - \$127,814 (*Arctic Alive! An Innovative E-Learning Environment*).
- BE/OPP-0119798: 09/01–08/03 - \$99,656 (*Human Dimensions of the Arctic System: A Workshop to Stimulate Research on the Dynamics of Coupled Natural and Human Systems*).

The work proposed for a new five-year cooperative agreement follows directly from the results of work from the previous cooperative agreement (2001–2006) described in this section. The results of prior work are described in four major categories: Arctic Community Science Planning, NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination, Arctic Science Education, and Information and Outreach. Building on the major accomplishments summarized below, ARCUS will continue to serve the goals of the NSF arctic programs.

ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research for 15 years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents to facilitate progress in programs and issues important to the NSF and the arctic research community.

Arctic Research Support and Logistics

The Arctic Research Support and Logistics Program at NSF supports a variety of activities related to research support, including long-term observations, data acquisition, facilities operation, and services that broadly support the arctic research community. ARCUS has a long history of working with the arctic research community to develop logistics strategies and recommendations. In 1997, ARCUS published

Logistics Recommendations for an Improved U.S. Arctic Research Capability, which provided effective guidance on logistics improvements to the U.S. Arctic Research Commission and to the NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) Arctic Sciences Section. In 2003, as a follow-up to that report, ARCUS published *Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-scale Studies in a Changing Environment*, summarizing progress made in improving research support since 1997 and responding with new recommendations for arctic logistics and research support. The recommendations led to several major improvements to logistics support infrastructure and funding and a National Academies study entitled “Designing an Arctic Observing Network”—the resulting report will provide guidance on the design of an arctic land, atmosphere, and ocean observing network.

In response to the need for comprehensive and coordinated information on terrestrial and ship-based research platforms and access throughout the Arctic, ARCUS initiated the Arctic Logistics Information and Support (ALIAS) project, collecting relevant logistics support information in an online database. The ALIAS website serves as a primary access point and information source that helps researchers assess the feasibility of working in a specific area or on a specific research platform, plan the conduct of research, view current research and research support resources, and make useful scientific and logistics contacts for planned research efforts. The ALIAS database contains information on over 90 vessels and research stations from 18 countries.

Another key research support and logistics issue, and one in which ARCUS has been involved over the past five years, is the management and integration of geospatial data. In 2001, ARCUS convened a community workshop to assess current capabilities and identify infrastructure and information needs for the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in arctic research. The results of this workshop were published by ARCUS in an online report entitled *Recommendations for a Geographic Information Infrastructure to Support Arctic Research: Outcomes of the Arctic GIS Workshop*. This report continues to provide guidance on developing arctic GIS activities

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: RESULTS OF PRIOR SUPPORT

and led to two follow-on meetings in 2003 organized by ARCUS on behalf of NSF. Participants at these meetings expressed the need for a centralized location to communicate arctic GIS activities, and ARCUS developed a website to provide coordinated information on arctic GIS. These activities have supported planning of ongoing arctic GIS programs, outreach and education activities, and arctic GIS International Polar Year efforts.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change and Bering Ecosystem Study Coordination and Planning

In recent years, scientists and local residents have observed a suite of environmental changes throughout the Arctic. NSF has supported a variety of research efforts focused on environmental change through interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches, requiring communication and coordination within and between diverse research communities; ARCUS has provided this key support for two research efforts: the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) and the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST).

In 2003, ARCUS organized and facilitated the first SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM). Over 440 researchers from around the world presented and discussed evidence of rapid environmental change in the Arctic. Through this meeting, SEARCH formed cooperative relationships with pertinent arctic science programs sponsored by other nations; over 20 side meetings were held in conjunction with the OSM to facilitate cooperative planning, including a workshop that led to the initiation of the International Study of Arctic Change. ARCUS compiled the abstracts from this meeting in *Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting*. In 2005, the SEARCH science management function transitioned from the University of Washington to ARCUS. As the SEARCH project office, ARCUS developed a new SEARCH website, appointed members to three SEARCH implementation panels, and organized planning teleconferences and electronic meetings. ARCUS, in collaboration with the SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) and Interagency Program Management Committee, convened the SEARCH Implementation Workshop in 2005 and published the workshop report: *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond*. The report serves as a point of reference for immediate planning for the International Polar Year and for an Arctic Observing

Network, and provides a perspective on SEARCH beyond immediate needs and priorities. ARCUS also developed and continues to distribute an informational brochure about the SEARCH program.

Another set of activities supported by ARCUS focuses on the productive and ecologically diverse Bering Sea. Recent evidence of change in this ecosystem has raised concerns and engendered research efforts by several agencies, including NSF. For the past several years, the Arctic Sciences Section has supported planning for the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST). ARCUS coordinated a 2003 working group meeting to develop a draft science plan, provided staff support for plan development, and published the resulting *BEST Science Plan* in 2004. ARCUS also worked closely with the University of Washington BEST project office to develop and finalize the *BEST Implementation Plan*, outlining the first phase of a ten-year research program focused on the marine ecosystems of the eastern Bering Sea and the people dependent on its resources. The first agency solicitation for BEST proposals was included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section announcement of opportunity; BEST research efforts will be a partial contribution to SEARCH.

NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

ARCUS has provided critical organizational support for several research programs in the NSF OPP Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program and the Arctic Social Sciences Program. These programs require collaborative planning among multiple diverse communities and disciplines.

Arctic System Science Program Coordination

Since its inception in 1989, researchers supported by the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program have worked to understand how the Arctic functions as a system and how it is connected with global processes. ARCUS has provided community science management, coordination, and facilitation for the ARCSS Program since 1992 with activities designed to facilitate the interdisciplinary and complex science planning necessary for system-scale science.

In 2002, ARCUS convened the second ARCSS All-Hands Workshop, gathering over 300 participants to discuss the state of knowledge about the arctic system and to plan the future of arctic system research. In 2003, ARCUS published *Proceedings of the Arctic System Science Program All-Hands Workshop 2002*,

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: RESULTS OF PRIOR SUPPORT

which has guided subsequent research planning efforts.

In 2002, following the All-Hands Workshop, the ARCSS Program entered a synthesis-driven phase, requiring broad community involvement in all phases of developing priorities, planning, and conducting research. ARCUS coordinated and facilitated several activities related to the synthesis approach in collaboration with the ARCSS Committee and NSF Program Director. Two ARCSS synthesis retreats were convened to distill and integrate current knowledge into a more holistic perspective of the arctic system. To build on retreat discussions and broaden participation, ARCUS convened several online meetings on synthesis planning. As a result of these discussions, two NSF ARCSS announcements of opportunity on “Synthesis of Arctic System Science” were released, one in 2004 and one in 2005. ARCUS has supported initial integration activities among the first set of funded synthesis projects through online meetings, teleconferences, and a planned workshop.

As the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO), ARCUS convenes online and in-person meetings for the ARCSS Program on a regular basis, involving participants from NSF, the ARCSS Committee, various science steering committees, and ARCSS investigators. ARCUS also distributes valuable information about the program, synthesis efforts, meetings, and funding opportunities through the website, e-mail listserves, and online meetings.

ARCUS also has conducted planning activities focused on thematic topics related to arctic system science. In 2001, ARCUS developed and published *The Hydrologic Cycle and its Role in Arctic and Global Environmental Change: A Rationale and Strategy for Synthesis Study*, which identifies gaps in understanding of arctic hydrological systems. The report and related white papers (Hinzman and Vörösmarty 2001) led to the development of the Freshwater Initiative, a set of NSF-funded projects that contributes to both ARCSS and SEARCH.

In addition, ARCUS has provided organizational support to the Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) program, which was created in 1997 as a component of ARCSS to better understand the role of humans in the arctic system. ARCUS established the HARC SMO in 2001 and, in this role, assisted the community in developing emerging research themes through in-person and online workshops, investigator meetings, and other means.

In 2004, the HARC project office transitioned to a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks; ARCUS continues to facilitate planning through maintaining the HARC website and coordination between HARC and the broader ARCSS Program.

Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

ARCUS provides support to the NSF Arctic Social Sciences Program by bringing together social scientists of diverse disciplines as well as researchers from other fields to promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and by working with the research community and arctic residents to develop science priorities and plans. ARCUS also supports information and outreach activities on behalf of the Program. All activities are designed to build partnerships and strengthen networks between relevant groups.

ARCUS has provided critical support for a community planning process for Bering Sea social science research. In 2003, as the BEST draft science plan (see page C-4) was introduced to the science community, Alaska Natives and social scientists recognized that a critical human dimension was missing from the substantive goals of the draft plan. In order to complement the existing *BEST Science Plan* and to capitalize on interest in collaborations among resident communities and scientists, a committee was organized to formulate a social science plan for the Bering Sea. In 2004, ARCUS convened a community forum to explore community research interests and to discuss the possible shape of the research plan. As a result of these discussions, a science advisory group, with support from ARCUS, drafted *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Plan*, which articulates a vision and approaches for social sciences research as a component of BEST. The draft document was posted online and is undergoing community review. A follow-up forum is planned for February 2006.

ARCUS has undertaken other community development and publication activities on behalf of the Arctic Social Sciences Program. In 2001, ARCUS provided support for 20 participants from the U.S. and Russia to attend the fourth International Congress of Arctic Social Scientists for a session on developing partnerships between researchers and stakeholders. In 2001, ARCUS coordinated the English translation and printing of *Den Nye Sikkerhed—Groenland I Et Sikkerhedspolitisk Perspektiv* (Greenland: Security Perspectives) as a resource for researchers planning

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: RESULTS OF PRIOR SUPPORT

to work in Greenland. In 2002, ARCUS prepared and printed *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*, which has been useful as a source of information on indigenous knowledge and as a tool for networking.

Arctic Section Science Materials

In addition to program-specific activities, ARCUS has accomplished activities that provide a service to NSF and the broad arctic research community.

In 2004, ARCUS coordinated community outreach and review for *Guidelines for Improved Cooperation Between Arctic Researchers and Northern Communities*, which was drafted by the Arctic Sciences Section and the Barrow Arctic Science Consortium. The document provides information and suggestions on improving the way researchers work with arctic communities while planning and conducting field research; the document has been printed for targeted meetings and is available online.

Community discussion about the timing of a new proposal deadline for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section led ARCUS to survey the U.S. arctic research community for feedback and recommendations on the best timing for an annual deadline in future years. Results from this survey were used by NSF when deciding on the new annual deadline of 10 November.

At the request of NSF, ARCUS produced two posters, *Arctic Science Discoveries* and *Arctic Science Education*, describing Arctic Sciences Section activities and programs. Resources like these improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS has long provided leadership within the arctic community to improve science education. In 2000, an Arctic Science Education Working Group sponsored by NSF and organized by ARCUS identified several challenges facing arctic science education programs, including: limited time, funding, knowledge (of, for example, technology necessary to communicate research, arctic cultures, and the arctic environment), and access to other relevant groups. ARCUS has undertaken many activities to address these challenges, including publication of an education report, implementing programs geared toward improving K–12 teaching and learning, and developing methods for sharing knowledge between relevant groups.

Arctic Science Education Report

In 2000, ARCUS convened a working group of researchers, educators, students, and arctic community representatives to develop recommendations on improving scientific literacy through focusing on arctic environment, culture, and research. The workshop results were published in *Arctic Science Education: Recommendations from the Working Group on Arctic Science Education to the National Science Foundation*. The report recommends approaches for engaging a broad audience in arctic research, building effective partnerships, and increasing public awareness; these recommendations continue to guide all aspects of ARCUS' education efforts.

Arctic Science Education Activities

In 2004, ARCUS planned and implemented the Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program in which K–12 teachers participate in arctic field projects and work with researchers to improve science education through experiences in scientific inquiry. Interest in the program has grown; to-date, over 200 teachers have applied to participate. Since 2004, 18 teachers have participated in the program traveling to 21 field sites in 6 countries. The program's online outreach elements have conveyed the research experience to broad audiences. Classrooms around the world have interacted with TREC teachers and researchers through live calls from the field and online bulletin boards.

In 2001, ARCUS developed, with funding from the NSF Geosciences Directorate, a pilot distance-delivery education program, *Arctic Alive!*, which allows students to participate in arctic research from the classroom by using technologies such as Internet presentations. The Arctic Sciences Section funded *Arctic Alive!* in its third year and ARCUS continues to incorporate program elements into existing educational programs, such as TREC.

In 2001–2003, ARCUS collaborated with several federal agencies and arctic communities to provide research experiences for arctic students and teachers through Eider Journey, a program that addresses issues of conservation and management of Steller's eiders. Through this program, students and teachers residing in the Arctic engaged in scientific research and received training in field methods, analysis, and hypothesis testing.

Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented an Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community, to promote communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents, and to improve public understanding of arctic research. Since the program's inception, a total of 49 speakers have addressed arctic issues at over 130 separate academic, K-12, and public engagements. The flexible nature of the program has provided a cost effective way for researchers and other arctic experts to share their knowledge in communities where they might not otherwise connect.

INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS' information and outreach activities disseminate information about a wide range of arctic research efforts to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and the public through the use of Internet tools, publications, and in-person meetings.

ARCUS Internet Resources

Website: The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs and various community science planning tools. It houses important information and resources about research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications and serves as a clearinghouse for all ARCUS activities. The website represents a valuable source of information for the public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, and access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.

ArcticInfo Listserve: The ArcticInfo listserv provides relevant and timely information about funding opportunities, events, publications, position announcements, and other news. Over 5,200 individuals subscribe and over 2,200 announcements have been posted since the listserv was created in 1996. The number of submissions for distribution and subscribers continues to increase each year.

Directory of Arctic Researchers: Initiated in 1994, the Directory of Arctic Researchers contains contact information and current research for individual arctic researchers in the U.S. and internationally. Regular surveys of individuals and institutions maintain

accuracy. The Directory now contains over 4,000 researchers and is available as a searchable database at the ARCUS website. The Directory facilitates networking and collaboration in research and education efforts between investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders.

Internet Media Archive: The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that are shared through the Internet. The IMA currently contains over 3,000 publicly accessible photos and media resources and provides the arctic research community a centralized location where images and video can be browsed and retrieved for a variety of uses.

Witness the Arctic Newsletter

Witness the Arctic has been published biannually since 1993 and provides information on current arctic research efforts and findings, research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic research, international activities, and profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts. The newsletter serves an audience of over 10,000 arctic scientists, educators, agency personnel, and policy makers and is available online and in print. All articles are thoroughly researched and edited before publication. ARCUS regularly receives positive feedback from subscribers describing how valuable they find this centralized source of detailed, relevant, and up-to-date information.

Arctic Community Outreach: Arctic Forum

The annual *Arctic Forum*, convened by ARCUS each year since 1994, brings together investigators, federal agency officials, students, and the public for presentations on cutting-edge arctic research, policy issues, and education. Since 2001, over 580 people have attended this meeting. Topical themes have included arctic environmental change, interactions between biological and physical systems, biocomplexity, resilience and vulnerability, sea ice dynamics, and arctic change and public literacy. The *Abstracts from the Arctic Forum* have been distributed to nearly 2,400 people. The meeting provides a unique opportunity for a diverse audience to share perspectives on topics and issues that cut across disciplines and agency missions; attendance continues to grow with an increasingly international audience. The interdisciplinary nature of this meeting has resulted in important contacts and collaborations among researchers, agencies, and countries that do not typically occur at discipline-focused gatherings.

PROPOSED COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT ACTIVITIES, 2006–2011

ARCUS proposes to the National Science Foundation's (NSF) Office of Polar Programs (OPP) a cooperative agreement over the next five years to provide organizational support to the NSF OPP Arctic Sciences Section to develop, promote, and implement arctic research and education. Building on its major accomplishments—outlined in the previous Results of Prior Support section—ARCUS will continue to serve the goals of the NSF arctic programs by nurturing the growth of arctic research through activities that cannot be accomplished as effectively by individual researchers, institutions, agencies, or by currently existing advisory bodies. Based on an excellent track record of prior work, and in cooperation with the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and the arctic science community, ARCUS proposes to carry out four major tasks to provide organizational support to the U.S. arctic science programs:

- Arctic Community Science Planning - coordinating science planning for the arctic research community across disciplinary and organizational boundaries;
- Arctic Sciences Section Coordination - support for research programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section—the Arctic System Science Program, the Arctic Natural Sciences Program, and the Arctic Social Sciences Program;
- Arctic Science Education - development and coordination of arctic science educational activities; and
- Information and Outreach - information and outreach activities disseminating timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, and the public.

An additional fifth task is the provision of core support for ARCUS' NSF-funded activities—dedicated funding of the costs incurred by program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects.

Much of the planning and organizing work conducted by ARCUS on behalf of the arctic research community consists of several related activities that are described here to outline the methods that ARCUS uses to achieve broad and consistent representation of the arctic research community:

- *Workshop and Meeting Coordination:* ARCUS works with the scientific community to determine the scope and focus of a workshop or planning meeting, including goals and objectives, important scientific topics, key participants, and the appropriate extent of community participation. Frequently, a small organizing committee is appointed and

ARCUS board members and staff meet before the Arctic Forum in 2004.

ARCUS works with the committee to develop the meeting program, invite speakers and participants, and plan the meeting logistics, including the venue, participant travel and lodging, and appropriate meet-

ing support. ARCUS provides information about the upcoming event to the relevant groups, or broadly via the ARCUS website, listserve, and other dissemination mechanisms.

- *Publication Development:* Many planning efforts organized by ARCUS have resulted in a publication summarizing the arctic research community's recommendations on a particular issue. ARCUS works with workshop participants and the scientific community to prepare draft content, requiring a clear understanding of the goals and context of the planning process, key scientific concepts, and the needs and priorities of the particular research community. Contributions must then be integrated, synthesized, and edited to present a coherent and compelling summary of the planning effort; and figures, graphics, and the basic report layout must be prepared in keeping with the contents of the report. All ARCUS reports are subjected to at least one round of review by the research community. In collaboration with the major contributors, ARCUS coordinates revisions of the draft report in response to review comments. The iterative review process and close collaboration with the research community results in substantive reports that reflect the views of the diverse scientific community. ARCUS also handles the publication process, including printing requirements, press

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

checks, and distribution of the finished reports in a timely manner.

- **Information and Communications Activities:** ARCUS delivers a wide range of community-relevant information in an efficient and timely manner. Several structured communication outreach activities, including the *Witness the Arctic* newsletter, the ArcticInfo listserv, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, and the ARCUS website were initially developed in response to requests for assistance or information from members of the scientific community. In addition to these structured activities, and because of our broad network of connections with individuals and institutions, ARCUS is often called on informally to provide information about arctic research efforts and resources. We frequently receive thanks from researchers, educators, and administrators for exposing them to relevant and important findings and issues that they would not have received through normal institutional or disciplinary channels.

The following proposed major tasks and project activities are listed by number to reference budget information available in the Budget Justification section.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

ARCUS has facilitated community science planning for arctic research efforts for over 15 years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS' work in science planning is characterized by a unique and notable ability to synthesize a broad spectrum of input and to facilitate planning from the development of early concepts to concrete plans and recommendations. ARCUS proposes to continue this work at several levels and through various methods, with activities focused on the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) program coordination, including a community-wide State of the Arctic Conference to be held in 2007, and Arctic Data Coordination.

Through synthesizing scientific information from many sources, ARCUS will provide the means for arctic researchers to translate broad scientific goals into specific and detailed implementation plans and to integrate and disseminate their research efforts effectively.

Activity 1.1: SEARCH Coordination

The Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) is an interagency effort to understand the nature, extent, and future development of the system-scale change presently seen in the Arctic with research spanning across arctic terrestrial, oceanic, atmospheric, and social systems. ARCUS

A map of priority areas for distributed ocean and sea ice observations published in the report from the SEARCH Implementation Workshop.

has served as the SEARCH project office since early 2005 and proposes continuing coordination activities in this capacity. Activities over the next five years will focus on working with the Science Steering Committee (SSC), implementation panels, working groups, agency representatives, and the

research community to facilitate

the growth of SEARCH to a fully-implemented and funded initiative, accomplished through the following mechanisms:

- **Support to SEARCH SSC, Panels, Working Groups:** SEARCH Science Management activities are guided by the SEARCH SSC, three implementation panels (Observing Change Panel, Understanding Change Panel, and Responding to Change Panel), and working groups that are convened as needed for specific activity areas (e.g., Data Management, Education and Outreach, Paleoenvironment). ARCUS will continue to provide organizational support to these groups to guide and coordinate implementation of SEARCH science activities. ARCUS will convene one SSC meeting per year, other work sessions, and regular teleconferences and webconferences as needed, and will provide staff support to the SSC Chair.
- **Development of Website and Internet Resources:**

ARCUS developed the SEARCH website, which provides a centralized source of information about the program.

ARCUS launched a new SEARCH website in 2005 as a tool for organizing and communicating SEARCH science, planning, and outreach activities. ARCUS will continue to develop the SEARCH website over the next five years with continual updates of information and resources on SEARCH

science, project activities, meetings, and coordination efforts with relevant national and international programs. A specific development effort will focus on increased content related to science findings and interactive online tools, including a SEARCH science bibliography and a searchable database of SEARCH projects and research activities.

- *State of the Arctic Conference 2007*: Several groups within the arctic research community have advocated for a community-wide international arctic conference to assess and communicate current scientific knowledge of arctic change. ARCUS will work with the international research community and relevant agencies to plan and convene a “State of the Arctic” conference in 2007 as an important component of the International Polar Year 2007–2008. The broad focus of the conference will be current research, existing gaps, and key research priorities; the specific focus and activities will be determined and refined in cooperation with representatives from the research community.
- *International Coordination*: SEARCH science activities are focused on the entire arctic region and thus require careful coordination and integration with ongoing and planned international activities. ARCUS will support the SEARCH SSC and Chair in collaborative planning and joint activities with relevant international programs, including the International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)—a long-term, international, cross-disciplinary, pan-arctic program that will document changes in the Arctic, as well as the Developing Arctic Modelling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES) project sponsored by the European Union.

Activity 1.2: Arctic Data Coordination

A clear need has emerged through a number of arctic planning activities, conferences, and meetings for improved arctic data coordination and management across disciplines, research programs, and agencies. There is a particularly strong need for coordination of geospatial data, as acquisition and development of such data has proliferated with tremendous potential for advancing science through a variety of cyberinfrastructure applications, including Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and related technologies. ARCUS has undertaken several activities related to data coordination efforts, including the coordination of three Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

workshops and creation of an Arctic GIS website. ARCUS will continue to facilitate the development of a coordinated approach and infrastructure to data management issues through online meetings and website tools. No budget is included for this activity because the planned level of effort is integrated within other activities.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

The research goal of the NSF Arctic Research Program is to gain a better understanding of the Earth’s biological, geophysical, chemical, and sociocultural processes, and the interactions of ocean, land, atmosphere, biological, and human systems. The NSF Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section supports a multitude of research activities, including field and modeling studies and data analysis. Over the past cooperative agreement, ARCUS has provided organizational support for several programs included in the Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section and proposes to continue support activities within the Arctic System Science Program (ARCSS), the Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP), and the Arctic Natural Sciences Program (ANS). The proposed work will advance knowledge and understanding of the Arctic across the physical, natural, and social domains through science planning activities that facilitate an integrated and interdisciplinary approach to arctic research.

Activity 2.1: ARCSS Program Coordination

The Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program addresses the physical, chemical, biological, and social processes of the Arctic and how these arctic systems interact with the Earth as a whole, including changes in the arctic system and their global ramifications. The goal of the ARCSS Program is to answer the following question: What do changes in the arctic system imply for the future? To address this question, researchers must:

- advance from a component understanding to a system understanding of the Arctic;
- understand the behavior of the arctic system—past, present, and future;
- understand the role of the Arctic as a component of the global system; and
- include society as an integral part of the arctic system.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

In response, the ARCSS Program strives towards an increasingly integrated, synthetic, and interdisciplinary approach. Currently, ARCUS provides community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF

Xiaoju Pan hauls in an active optics package on the icebreaker USCGC Healy during the May 2004 Shelf-Basin Interactions (SBI) cruise. Photo by Patty Cie, 2004 TREC teacher.

Arctic System Science Program as the ARCSS Science Management Office (SMO); ARCUS will support the continuing progress of the ARCSS Program through the following activities for the next five-year period, with increased community input and development of a new ARCSS Program science planning process:

- *ARCSS Committee Coordination:* ARCUS will continue to provide organizational support for the ARCSS Committee (AC), including coordinating AC review of accomplishments, priorities, and gaps in ARCSS research activities and projects as well as disseminating relevant information to the research community. ARCUS will convene two AC meetings per year (often overlapping with related principal investigator meetings), other work sessions as necessary, regular teleconferences and web meetings, and will provide staff support to the AC Chair.
- *Community Webconferences:* ARCUS will continue to organize and support a variety of community webconferences, including eTown Meetings—open online community meetings focused on ARCSS planning and programmatic issues, and Webseminars—community-organized online seminars on scientific topics relevant to arctic system research, important scientific questions, or collaborative planning for research endeavors.
- *All-Hands Workshop 2008:* ARCUS will organize and support a third ARCSS All-Investigator workshop in 2008 (the first two workshops were held in 1997 and 2002) to further advance interdisciplinary and system-science goals of the ARCSS Program. The focus and activities will be determined in deliberations with the AC, the ARCSS Program Director, and relevant community groups.
- *Website Development:* A complete reorganization and launching of the ARCSS website is planned for the current cooperative agreement year; over the

next five years, ARCUS will continue to develop and improve the ARCSS website as a central point for organizing and communicating ARCSS Program activities, including information and resources on community planning efforts, funding opportunities, ARCSS research, meetings, and publications.

- *HARC Project Office:* The Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) is a component of ARCSS that was created in 1997 with the aim to better understand the role of humans in the functioning of and interactions among the various physical, biological, and social components of the arctic system and the significance of changes in the arctic system for people in the Arctic and across the globe. ARCUS will continue to facilitate planning for the HARC program, for one additional year, in collaboration with the HARC Science Management Office, currently at the University of Alaska Fairbanks, through hosting and maintaining the website and coordination between HARC and the broader ARCSS Program.

Activity 2.2: Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination

The Arctic Natural Sciences (ANS) Program is a multidisciplinary program within the NSF Office of Polar Programs Arctic Sciences Section that supports research in the atmospheric sciences, biological sciences, earth sciences, glaciology, and oceanography. ARCUS will coordinate ANS science planning activities related to the Bering Sea, a region that is ecologically diverse and economically and culturally important.

- *Activity 2.2.1: Bering Sea Research Coordination:* The Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) is a comprehensive research program resulting from planning that began in 2004. Priorities for research were published in the *BEST Science Plan* in October 2004 and were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section announcement of opportunity. ARCUS will provide organizational assistance to this program through support of meetings (in-person, online, and teleconference) and activities of the Science Steering Committee (SSC) and funded Principal Investigators as well as continued website development and maintenance.

Bering Ecosystem Study Science Plan published by ARCUS in 2004.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

Activity 2.3: Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination

The Arctic Social Sciences Program (ASSP) is a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary program that encompasses all social sciences research supported by NSF. The Arctic Social Sciences Program supports research that documents and analyzes the dynamic cultures, economies, and technologies of northern populations. ARCUS will provide support to the Arctic Social Sciences Program by bringing together social scientists of diverse disciplines as well as researchers from other fields to promote cross-disciplinary collaboration; by working with the research community and arctic residents to develop science priorities and plans; and by supporting information and outreach activities.

- *Activity 2.3.1: Bering Sea Community Coordination.* ARCUS has provided support for the development of a plan for Bering Sea social science research and the plan's integration and implementation with the current *Bering Sea Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan* (see page C-4). ARCUS will continue to work with the Bering Sea community steering committee to support activities related to science plan development through teleconference/webconference coordination, publication support, and similar organizational support activities as requested by the NSF ASSP Program Manager and relevant communities.
- *Activity 2.3.2: Arctic Social Sciences Coordination.* ARCUS will implement a variety of information and outreach and coordination activities to bring together social scientists as well as researchers from other fields to promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and to assist the research community and arctic residents in developing science priorities and plans. Activities will include updating and maintenance of the International Directory of Arctic Social Scientists, which will be made publicly available through a searchable, easily updated online database.

A poster created by ARCUS for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section. Resources like this are routinely used at scientific conferences and improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic.

Activity 2.4: Arctic Section Science Materials

ARCUS will, in collaboration with NSF program staff, develop information and communication resources such as posters and brochures that reach across geographic, cultural, institutional, and disciplinary barriers to assist planning and integration of diverse research efforts and to improve awareness of NSF-sponsored research in the Arctic. ARCUS will produce materials that present information on research and educational activities in a clear and compelling way, providing a valuable resource for networking and outreach activities to relevant communities and for meetings, workshops, and conferences.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

ARCUS' education programs have been developed around several guiding principles formulated through community workshops and work with researchers, educators, students, and residents of the Arctic. These principles are:

- Education programs must be relevant, inquiry-based, and, if focused on K–12, they should align with National Science Education Standards.
- Education development should build on existing education efforts; the community should focus on increased collaborations between established

Students participating in the NSF Research Experience for Undergraduates program look at weather data collected in Norway. Photo by Sandra Geisbush, 2004 TREC teacher.

programs and networks and should build supportive partnerships between researchers, educators and schools, and communities.

- Arctic residents must be involved in developing and implementing educational programs and effective partnerships must be promoted and nurtured.
- There is a need for increased awareness or “visibility” of the arctic region and its residents, the unique and analogous aspects of the Arctic as a polar region, and its role in the Earth system.
All of ARCUS education programs fit into this context and are developed to:
 - Ensure that high-quality information and education in arctic science is available to the general public, students and teachers, and Natives of the Arctic.
 - Enable interested and talented students to pursue scientific careers in the Arctic.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

- Ensure that the scientific and technical workforce exists to meet the challenges of the arctic research agenda.

ARCUS will continue to provide an educational leadership role within the arctic community through two major activities designed to bridge arctic research and education:

- **Activity 3.1: Arctic Science Education Activities.** In 2004, ARCUS initiated the Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program, an educational research experience in which K–12 teachers participate in arctic field projects, working with researchers to improve science education through experiences in scientific inquiry. ARCUS will continue development of Teacher Research Experience (TRE) activities in order to provide necessary training, infrastructure, and professional development support needed to improve K–12 and public understanding of arctic science. ARCUS will support activities for 10 teachers annually to participate in TREs to increase their content knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the public and the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and participate in a supportive long-term network of researchers and education colleagues. Specific activities will include an annual teacher orientation and training, maintenance and development of a comprehensive website featuring journals from the field and interactive bulletin boards, and support of web conferences from the field.
- **Activity 3.2: Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series.** ARCUS initiated the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community and to nurture better understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents. ARCUS proposes to continue the visiting speakers' series at a modest level, sponsoring up to 15 speakers each year over the next five years, with an increased focus on local community participation. This cost-effective means for improving interactions among individual researchers and institutions engaged in arctic research

Richard Glenn talks about baleen during his 2001 Arctic Visiting Speaker tour to an elementary school in Texas. Photo courtesy of Ken Dunton.

will promote productive collaborations between researchers and arctic communities and broaden the educational opportunities available to students interested in arctic research. ARCUS will also continue to provide detailed descriptions of Arctic Visiting Speaker tours and update and expand the information available in the Speakers' Bureau—a catalog of distinguished arctic researchers, policy makers, and educators available on the ARCUS website.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel providing information about current research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public. To be effective, the broad dissemination of information and resources on arctic research must be accomplished through several methods, including newsletters, electronic communications, forums like the ARCUS-sponsored *Arctic Forum*, and workshops:

- **Activity 4.1: Witness the Arctic: Chronicles of the NSF Arctic Sciences Program.** *Witness the Arctic* is a newsletter that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. ARCUS will continue to produce bi-annual issues over the next five years (8 issues due to timing with current cooperative agreement) with a broad spectrum of lead stories, planning updates for major research initiatives and programs, information relevant to national and international arctic policy matters, innovative arctic science education activities, relevant national and international research and coordination efforts, and arctic science activities of U.S. universities and research institutes.
- **Activity 4.2: ARCUS Website.** The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community. The website serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages and acts as a cohesive focal point for NSF Arctic Sciences Section activities. The ARCUS website represents a valuable source of information for the general public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, and access to other researchers, programs, and stakehold-

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

ers working in the Arctic. ARCUS will continue with daily updates and development of the website, including ongoing improvement to site architecture, design and code standards, and content development. Specific developments over the next five years will include interactive database resource tools such as searchable bibliographies and project databases and community workspaces, whereby workgroup members can share and edit files, create webpages, and communicate via bulletin boards.

The ARCUS website on the Internet at www.arcus.org.

- **Activity 4.3: ArcticInfo.** ARCUS proposes to continue developing and maintaining ArcticInfo, the primary email listserv for the arctic research community. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other useful news. Management of the listserv is time-intensive and requires understanding of arctic research issues as well as excellent editorial skills. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website. Over 5,200 researchers currently subscribe to ArcticInfo and the subscription list grows daily.

In addition to ArcticInfo, ARCUS will continue to maintain and manage several additional email listserves for the research community, ranging from small email groups for project team members to program-focused moderated email listserves, such as ARCSS and SEARCH listserves.

- **Activity 4.4: Directory of Arctic Researchers.** The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to facilitate networking and collaboration in arctic research and education efforts between individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders. The contents of the Directory, which now includes information on over 4,000 U.S. and international arctic researchers, are developed through surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions. ARCUS proposes to continue maintenance and expansion of the online version of the Directory. In particular, developments and improvements over the next five years will include continual addition of database entries, development of an automated daily update, and establishment of

web services that allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases, such as the VECO Polar Resources project database.

- **Activity 4.5: Internet Media Archive.**

ARCUS was funded through the last cooperative agreement with NSF to develop a graphics and media archive depicting research-related information (figures, photographs, maps, logos, etc.) and to make them available via the Internet. The resulting ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are shared through the ARCUS website; the IMA

The IMA provides a centralized location where images and other media resources can be browsed online for use in publications, presentations, or websites.

now contains nearly 3,000 publicly accessible photos and media resources and approximately 8,000 additional resources that are being prepared for public access. ARCUS will continue improvement and expansion of the IMA over the next five years, with a particular focus on graphics depicting key arctic research results and findings as well as edited video archives of relevant scientific community meetings.

- **Activity 4.6: Arctic Research Broader Impacts Showcase (ARBIS).** As part of the NSF merit review criteria, all proposals are evaluated for "broader impacts," namely the promotion of teaching, training, and learning; broadening participation of underrepresented groups; enhancing infrastructure for research and education; broad dissemination of research results; and benefits to society. There are myriad ways in which the broader impacts criterion is met by individual investigators, project teams, and programs. There does not exist, however, a coordinated method in which examples of broader impacts activities can be documented, stored, and communicated to a broad audience, including the research community, NSF, and the public. In response to this need, ARCUS proposes to develop an online "Arctic Research Broader Impacts Showcase (ARBIS)"—an interactive catalog of text, photo and media documentation that will allow members of the research community to upload, store, and share broader impacts activities and accomplishments.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION: PROPOSED ACTIVITIES

- **Activity 4.7: Arctic Community Outreach.**
ARCUS proposes to continue to conduct a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic. As part of this activity, ARCUS will continue to organize the annual 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' Annual Meeting in the Washington, D.C. area. The *Arctic Forum* brings together investigators, federal agency officials, students, and the public for presentations on new and cutting-edge arctic research, policy issues, and education, and has served to provide a critical and unique venue to discuss and address important arctic research issues. Additional outreach activities include the preparation of posters or presentations on request; participation in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities; and sponsorship of arctic networking activities at conferences or through online meetings.

ARCUS has published proceedings from the annual Arctic Forum since 1998.

5. CORE SUPPORT

The current ARCUS-NSF cooperative agreement budget includes a category called Core Support that funds program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement projects and cannot be attributed to a specific project. These costs are distinguished from indirect costs because they directly relate to programmatic activities rather than to the administrative infrastructure. The inclusion of funds that are not specific to particular projects or activities, which vary tremendously over the course of the five-year cooperative agreement period, adds stability to the operation of the organization and the staff team as well as providing crucial support that addresses multiple tasks and activities. The Core Support category is again included in this proposal and incorporates:

- Salaries and benefits of the Executive Director for program management and oversight of multiple cooperative agreement activities when this direction and oversight is not dedicated to one specific activity or project;
- Hardware and software technology to provide particular system or technical capability required of multiple cooperative agreement activities;
- Communications requirements specifically needed to support multiple cooperative agreement activities;
- Salaries and benefits for the Systems Administrator for the portion of time spent developing or supporting capabilities required by multiple cooperative agreement activities and not dedicated to a specific activity or project; and
- Staff travel to conferences and meetings to maintain and improve knowledge and understanding of NSF arctic science interests, when this participation is not specific to one cooperative agreement activity.

SUMMARY

The activities described in this proposal provide part of the essential underpinning for successful research and education in and about the Arctic by facilitating science, education, and outreach through tasks that would be impossible for individual investigators to accomplish. Effective planning and the timely transfer of information among scientists and between the practicing science community and NSF are critical to the quality of the science that is conducted and to the efficient allocation of limited resources. As the emphasis on accountability and public awareness of science grows, ARCUS provides valuable information, education, and outreach resources for the arctic research community. As the results of prior work show, ARCUS is well qualified to carry out the proposed tasks. The proposed work will significantly improve communication, integration, and coordination of research and education efforts, thus improving decision-making concerning the Arctic—a region undergoing profound change and an integral part of global natural and social systems.

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- Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). 2005. *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond*. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 90 pages.
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Principal Investigator: Wendy K. Warnick

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Fairbanks, AK 99709

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E-mail: warnick@arcus.org

I. PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION

N/A

II. APPOINTMENTS

1994 to present - Executive Director, Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.

1997 to present - Ex-officio member of the ARCUS Board of Directors

1992 to 1994 - Program Manager, Arctic Research Consortium of the United States

Prior to 1992 - Twenty years experience in planning, coordination, program administration, community health and policy education, and arctic issues, including:

- Executive Director, Interior Alaska Economic Development Council
- Executive Director, Child, Adolescent, and Family Services, Fairbanks Community Mental Health Center
- Consultant/Trainer/Instructor, (1) State of Alaska Department of Public Safety; (2) State of Alaska Division of Mental Health and Developmental Disabilities; (3) various Alaskan communities, and national and state non-profit organizations
- Program Director, Alaska Northern Region Child Sexual Abuse Task Force
- Renewable Energy and Appropriate Technology Consultant, Northern Alaska Environmental Center
- Assistant Manager, University of Alaska Musk Ox Project

III. PUBLICATIONS

Publications most closely related to the proposed project.

Co-author or managing editor of the following publications published by ARCUS, most of which can be located on the Internet at www.arcus.org/Publications/index.html:

Arctic Science Education: Recommendations from the Working Group on Arctic Science Education to the National Science Foundation. 2002. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 56 pages.

Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program. 2003. *Proceedings of the Arctic System Science Program All-Hands Workshop 2002.* Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 271 pages.

Schlosser, P., W. Tucker, W. Warnick, and A. York, eds. 2003. *Arctic Research Support and Logistics: Strategies and Recommendations for System-scale Studies in a Changing Environment.* Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 95 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). 2005. *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond.* Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 90 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). 2005. *Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 27–30 October 2003, Seattle, Washington.* Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 334 pages.

Other significant publications, whether or not related to the proposed project.

Managing or advisory editor of the following publications published by ARCUS, all of which can be located on the internet at www.arcus.org/Publications/index.html:

Abstracts from the Arctic Forum. 1998–2005. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. Various pages.

Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST) Science Plan. 2004. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 82 pages.

Krupnik, I., and D. Jolly, eds. 2002. *The Earth is Faster Now: Indigenous Observations of Arctic Environmental Change*. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 384 pages.

SEARCH: The Study of Environmental Arctic Change. 2001. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. Brochure.

Witness the Arctic. 1993–2005. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. Vol. 1–11, various pages.

IV. SYNERGISTIC ACTIVITIES

- Coordinates interdisciplinary, integrative scientific planning and supervises preparation of synthesis reports.
- Identifies individuals in the research community appropriate for various forms of collaboration on a formal and informal basis; and conceived and developed the Directory of Arctic Researchers and ArcticInfo, both of which have facilitated countless collaborations.
- Facilitated development and implementation of education project mentoring students with disabilities for careers in math, science, and engineering in the Arctic.
- Works to broaden outreach to Alaska native community through education programs and integration of Traditional Knowledge into programs of ARCUS.
- Encourages young researchers through implementation of ARCUS student award program.

V. COLLABORATIONS & OTHER AFFILIATIONS

Ms. Warnick works extensively with a large number of arctic researchers, educators, and indigenous peoples representatives.

Helen V. Wiggins

Program Coordinator, ARCUS

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Fairbanks, AK 99709

Phone: 907-474-1600 • Fax: 907-474-1604

E-mail: helen@arcus.org

I. PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION

University of Maryland	Geography	B.S. 1995
University of Georgia	Geography	M.A. 1999
University of Georgia	Geography	Ph.D. Program (degree not awarded)

II. APPOINTMENTS

2004 to present – Program Coordinator, ARCUS

2003 to 2004 – Project Manager, ARCUS

1999 to 2000 – Research Technician III, Savannah River Ecology Laboratory

1997 to 1999 – Teaching Assistant, University of Georgia

1997 – GIS Analyst, S.C. Department of Health & Environmental Control

1995 to 1997 – Project Leader, University of Maryland Spatial Analysis Laboratory

III. PUBLICATIONS

Publications most related to the proposed project:

Editor of the following publications published by ARCUS:

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). 2005. *Study of Environmental Arctic Change: Plans for Implementation During the International Polar Year and Beyond*. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 90 pages.

Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH). 2005. *Proceedings of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, 27–30 October 2003, Seattle, Washington*. Fairbanks, AK: Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. 334 pages.

Other publications:

Foresman, T.W., H.V. Wiggins, and D.L. Porter. 1996. Metadata Myth: Misunderstanding the Implications of Federal Metadata Standards. First IEEE Metadata Conference. Silver Spring, MD.

Foresman, T.W., H.V. Wiggins, D.L. Porter, P. Masuoka, and W. Acevedo. 1996. Design and Documentation of a Baltimore-Washington Regional Spatial Data Testbed for Environmental Model Calibration and Verification. Third International Conference on Integrating Geographic Information and Environmental Modeling. Sante Fe, NM.

Parker, A.J., Parker, K.C. and H. Wiggins-Brown. 2000. Disturbance and Scale Effects on Southern Old-Growth Forests (USA): The Sand Pine Example. *Natural Areas Journal*, 20:273-279.

IV. SYNERGISTIC ACTIVITIES

Most ARCUS activities serve to broaden the impact of arctic research. Specific examples of Ms. Wiggins' contributions include key involvement in:

- development of a SEARCH project database to support coordination and cooperation within the scientific community and among funding agencies;
- coordinating interdisciplinary, integrative scientific planning for the SEARCH and ARCSS programs;

- adapting online communications tools for the TREC program to allow teachers and researchers to connect with geographically dispersed classrooms and the public through use of online teacher and researcher journals, message boards, photo albums, real-time presentations and calls from the field, and online learning resources;
- providing professional development opportunities for teachers with online content, tools, and seminars geared towards subject matter learning, teaching practices, and alignment of research experiences with current professional and teaching standards; and
- integrating research and education by supporting a sustained community of teachers, scientists, and the public through online seminars, an e-mail listserv, and teacher-to-teacher peer groups.

V. COLLABORATIONS & OTHER AFFILIATIONS

Through her current professional appointment, Ms. Wiggins works and collaborates with a large number of members of the arctic research community

Graduate Advisors:

Dr. Albert Parker, University of Georgia

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	12.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 102,960			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	12.00	0.00	0.00	102,960			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	12.00	0.00	0.00	485,294			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				13,475			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				96,603			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					698,332		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					265,367		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					963,699		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					92,300		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					2,663		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS	\$ 8,000						
2. TRAVEL	206,100						
3. SUBSISTENCE	200,375						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (229)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	414,475		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					47,380		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					77,670		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					91,500		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					13,500		
5. SUBAWARDS					95,000		
6. OTHER					213,225		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					538,275		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					2,011,412		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 1916412)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					728,237		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					2,739,649		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 2,739,649	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 2

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	12.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 108,108			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	12.00	0.00	0.00	108,108			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	12.00	0.00	0.00	507,588			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				14,175			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				97,148			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				727,019			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				276,269			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				1,003,288			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				83,425			
2. FOREIGN				2,663			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____	8,000						
2. TRAVEL _____	149,400						
3. SUBSISTENCE _____	145,250						
4. OTHER _____	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (166)				302,650			
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				47,250			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				41,898			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				97,500			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				13,500			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				79,350			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				279,498			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				1,671,524			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 1671524)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				635,179			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				2,306,703			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 2,306,703			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 3

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	12.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 113,537			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	12.00	0.00	0.00	113,537			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	12.00	0.00	0.00	532,739			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				14,875			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				101,774			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					762,925		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					289,913		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					1,052,838		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL					81,000		
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN					2,700		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$	8,000						
2. TRAVEL	116,550						
3. SUBSISTENCE	110,250						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (126)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	234,800		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					46,850		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					56,796		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					96,500		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					13,500		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					79,350		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					292,996		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					1,664,334		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 1664334)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					632,447		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					2,296,781		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 2,296,781	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 4

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PI, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	12.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 119,340			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	12.00	0.00	0.00	119,340			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	12.00	0.00	0.00	559,208			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				15,610			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				106,630			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					800,788		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					304,302		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					1,105,090		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL							
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)					62,050		
2. FOREIGN					2,738		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____			8,000				
2. TRAVEL _____			110,200				
3. SUBSISTENCE _____			101,500				
4. OTHER _____			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (116)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	219,700		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					46,750		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					56,636		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					71,100		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					13,500		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					79,350		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					267,336		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					1,656,914		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 1656914)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					629,627		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					2,286,541		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)					\$ 2,286,541	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PI NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 5

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	12.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 125,424		\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	12.00	0.00	0.00	125,424			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (11) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	12.00	0.00	0.00	587,587			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				16,450			
5. (3) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				112,322			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				841,783			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				319,881			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				1,161,664			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)				59,200			
2. FOREIGN				2,775			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____			8,000				
2. TRAVEL _____			93,600				
3. SUBSISTENCE _____			84,000				
4. OTHER _____			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (96) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS				185,600			
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				46,550			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				64,417			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				73,100			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				13,500			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				79,350			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				276,917			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				1,686,156			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 1686156)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				640,739			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				2,326,895			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 2,326,895	\$		
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	60.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 569,369			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	60.00	0.00	0.00	569,369			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (55) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	60.00	0.00	0.00	2,672,416			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (5) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				74,585			
5. (15) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				514,477			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				3,830,847			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				1,455,732			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				5,286,579			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL				377,975			
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN				13,539			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$	40,000						
2. TRAVEL	675,850						
3. SUBSISTENCE	641,375						
4. OTHER	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (733)				1,357,225			
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				234,780			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				297,417			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				429,700			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				67,500			
5. SUBAWARDS				95,000			
6. OTHER				530,625			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				1,655,022			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				8,690,340			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				3,266,229			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				11,956,569			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 11,956,569			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION: ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE U.S. ARCTIC SCIENCE PROGRAM, 2006–2011

The \$11,956,569 budget described in detail below would fund the activities included in the proposed five-year cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (NSF) for the period 1 July 2006 through 30 June 2011. The projects and activities described in this cooperative agreement proposal are primarily to continue work currently funded by the NSF under a previous five-year cooperative agreement, OPP-0101279. All of the activities described here are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' ongoing work for the National Science Foundation (NSF), providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs. The proposed activities will be conducted under five major tasks: Arctic Community Science Planning, Arctic Sciences Section Coordination, Arctic Science Education, Information and Outreach, and Core Support. Allocation of the requested funding by major task is represented graphically on page F-3 of the Budget Justification. Additional information about the budget detail is included after this narrative description in three budget explanation spreadsheets that:

1. summarize the costs by major task and project activity,
2. provide cost detail for each project activity (with activities numbered to match the identifying numbers in the proposal narrative), and
3. summarize the costs over the five-year period by Form 1030 category.

The cooperative agreement proposal budget includes:

Item A: Senior Personnel

Funds totalling \$569,369 are requested for the Executive Director position for the five-year cooperative agreement. The Executive Director provides program management and general guidance and direction for the community science management activities included in the cooperative agreement and also has oversight on the successful execution of all projects and tasks.

Item B: Other Personnel

Resources totaling \$3,261,478 are requested for a total of 15 staff positions during the five-year cooperative agreement period. The allocation of staff resources by activity over the five-year period is represented graphically on page F-4 of the Budget Justification.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

ARCUS charges actual fringe benefits costs on direct salaries. The fringe rate for budgeting purpose is 38% and totals \$1,455,732.

Item E: Travel

Funds totaling \$391,514 are requested to support staff travel to planned events, conferences, and workshops during the five-year agreement. Travel funds will support staff participation in SEARCH, BEST, and ARCSS Program workshops, and in various Information and Outreach program activities, including the *Arctic Forum*. This request includes \$377,975 for domestic travel and \$13,539 for foreign travel. The Year 1 request includes support for the State of the Arctic conference, co-sponsored by SEARCH through NSF, in collaboration with other federal agencies and various international entities and organizations.

Items F: Participant Support

Funds totaling \$1,357,225 are requested for participant support for a total of 733 participants during the five-year agreement. This line covers travel, subsistence, and stipend costs for research community participation at meetings, conferences and workshops for SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, BEST and the Bering Sea community

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

partnership activities, the *Arctic Forum*, part of the Community Outreach activity, and Arctic Science Education activities, including the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series and the Teacher Research Experiences program. The Year 1 request includes participant support for key invited participants for the State of the Arctic conference, co-sponsored by SEARCH through NSF, in collaboration with other federal agencies and various international entities and organizations.

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Line 1. Materials and Supplies

Resources totaling \$234,780 are requested to support the typical materials costs for the proposed program activities over the five-year period.

Line 2. Publication/Documentation and Dissemination

The cost of printing and distributing recommendations and proceedings from the 2007 State of the Arctic Conference, the social sciences plan "Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem," a SEARCH report in 2010, the annual *Arctic Forum* proceedings, and eight issues of the newsletter *Witness the Arctic* will be \$297,417.

Line 3. Consultant Services

Consulting agreements totaling \$429,700 for scientific, professional, or technical leadership or expertise will support SEARCH coordination, the ARCSS Program community science management leadership and synthesis coordination, Arctic Science Education Activities (for program evaluation services and field safety training), development of Internet resources, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, the Internet Media Archive, and Core Support activities.

Line 4. Computer Services

To facilitate and support the SEARCH coordination activities, ARCSS Program community science planning, and Arctic Science Education activities, computer support services totaling \$50,625 are anticipated. An additional \$16,875 will be spent in the area of Core Support activities for services that simultaneously address the needs of more than one activity.

Line 5. Subawards

Funds totaling \$95,000 are requested for subawards to the University of Alaska Fairbanks, for one year, to support the Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) project office; and to the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL), for one year, to support a dedicated synthesis coordinator for the ARCSS Program projects included in the Study of Northern Alaska Coastal Systems (SNACS).

Line 6. Other

Resources totaling \$530,625 are requested to cover the cost of conference, workshop, and meeting support and other miscellaneous communication expenses for SEARCH planning, ARCSS Program meetings and workshops, the Bering Ecosystem community partnership development meetings, and the annual *Arctic Forum*. The Year 1 request includes meeting support and communications costs for the State of the Arctic conference, co-sponsored by SEARCH through NSF, in collaboration with other federal agencies and various international entities and organizations.

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The ARCUS maximum provisional rate is currently 38% and has been used for budgeting purposes for the five-year term. The current ARCUS NSF cooperative agreement allows charging of indirect costs to Participant Support, which, for the purposes of this proposal, has been kept in the base of \$8,595,340. Indirect costs are not charged to subawards.

ALLOCATION OF REQUESTED FUNDING BY MAJOR TASK OVER THE FIVE-YEAR PERIOD OF THE COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT BUDGET

ALLOCATION OF STAFF RESOURCES BY ACTIVITY OVER THE FIVE-YEAR PERIOD OF THE COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT BUDGET

Summary of Proposed Funding by Major Task and Project Activities

1/21/06 12:41

	<u>Year 1</u>	<u>Year 2</u>	<u>Year 3</u>	<u>Year 4</u>	<u>Year 5</u>	<u>Total</u>
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 SEARCH Coordination	635159	227869	278149	240953	252156	1634287
Subtotal Direct Costs	635159	227869	278149	240953	252156	1634286
Indirect Costs	241362	86592	105698	91561	95821	621034
	876521	314461	383847	332514	347977	2255320
2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION						
2.1 <i>ARCSS Program Coordination</i>						
2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination	372266	393702	283558	267084	276665	1593275
2.2 <i>Arctic Natural Sciences Program Coordination</i>						
2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination	45899	43595	44929	64813	47753	246989
2.3 <i>Arctic Social Sciences Program Coordination</i>						
2.3.1 Bering Sea Community Coordination	38911	17440	18308	19203	20177	114039
2.3.2 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination	14421	8763	9205	9660	10143	52192
Subtotal Direct Costs	53332	26203	27513	28863	30320	166231
2.4 <i>Arctic Section Science Materials</i>						
2.4.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	13345	12074	12664	13296	13963	65342
Direct Costs - Arctic Section	484842	475574	368664	374056	368701	2071837
Indirect Costs	148139	180718	140092	142142	140106	751197
	632981	656292	508756	516198	508807	2823034
3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION						
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	128413	132535	137098	141934	147122	687102
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	41294	44524	45635	46752	47987	226192
Subtotal Direct Costs	169707	177059	182733	188686	195109	913294
Indirect Costs	64489	67282	69438	71701	74141	347051
	234196	244341	252171	260387	269250	1260345
4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH						
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	112455	100953	120178	124051	112676	570313
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	107388	112052	117104	122371	128140	587055
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	25033	27443	28824	30199	31728	143227
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	25318	30617	32175	33620	36285	158015
4.5 Internet Media Archive	48502	56606	59018	61485	64233	289844
4.6 Arctic Research Broader Impacts	40814	44607	46741	49053	51500	232715
4.7 Arctic Community Outreach	163193	172065	176488	170022	174716	856484
Subtotal Direct Costs	522703	544343	580528	590801	599278	2837653
Indirect Costs	198627	206849	220600	224504	227724	1078304
	721330	751192	801128	815305	827002	3915957
5. CORE SUPPORT						
5.1 Core Support	199001	246679	254260	262418	270912	1233270
Subtotal Direct Costs	199001	246679	254260	262418	270912	1233270
Indirect Costs	75620	93738	96619	99719	102947	468643
	274621	340417	350879	362137	373859	1701913
TOTAL	2739649	2306703	2296781	2286541	2326895	11956569

Estimated Indirect Cost Rate 38.00% 38.00% 38.00% 38.00% 38.00%

Proposed Funding Detail by Project Activities

	<u>2006</u>	<u>2007</u>	<u>2008</u>	<u>2009</u>	<u>2010</u>	<u>Total</u>
1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING						
1.1 <u>SEARCH Coordination</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	183,081	143,621	150,274	157,723	165,911	800,610
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	30,175	10,650	18,000	9,125	5,550	73,500
Participant Support Costs	248,500	53,250	90,000	54,750	37,000	483,500
Materials and Supplies	7,700	300	500	300	200	9,000
Publications/Dissemination	12,128	473	800	480	23,920	37,801
Consulting	-	1,000	-	-	1,000	2,000
Computer Services	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	16,875
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	150,200	15,200	15,200	15,200	15,200	211,000
Total direct costs	635,159	227,869	278,149	240,953	252,156	1,634,286
Total indirect costs	241,362	86,592	105,698	91,561	95,821	621,034
	876,521	314,461	383,847	332,514	347,977	2,255,320

Subtotal Direct	635,159	227,869	278,149	240,953	252,156	1,634,286
Subtotal Indirect	241,362	86,592	105,698	91,561	95,821	621,034
Total Community Science Planning	876,521	314,461	383,847	332,514	347,977	2,255,320

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.1.1 ARCSS Coordination

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	156,451	163,296	171,393	179,869	189,000	860,009
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,325	15,975	5,400	5,475	5,550	37,725
Participant Support Costs	40,500	138,125	32,000	32,375	32,750	275,750
Materials and Supplies	200	750	150	150	150	1,400
Publications/Dissemination	415	1,181	240	240	240	2,316
Consulting	63,000	63,000	63,000	37,600	37,600	264,200
Computer Services	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	16,875
Subawards	95,000	-	-	-	-	95,000
Other Direct Costs	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	40,000
Total direct costs	372,266	393,702	283,558	267,084	276,665	1,593,275
Total indirect costs	105,361	149,607	107,752	101,492	105,133	569,345
	477,627	543,309	391,310	368,576	381,798	2,162,620

2.2 ARCTIC NATURAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 Bering Sea Research Coordination

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	18,865	20,162	21,169	22,218	23,343	105,757
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	5,325	5,325	5,400	5,475	5,550	27,075
Participant Support Costs	21,300	17,750	18,000	36,500	18,500	112,050
Materials and Supplies	120	100	100	200	100	620
Publications/Dissemination	189	158	160	320	160	987
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	100	100	100	100	100	500
Total direct costs	45,899	43,595	44,929	64,813	47,753	246,989
Total indirect costs	17,441	16,566	17,073	24,629	18,146	93,855
	63,340	60,161	62,002	89,442	65,899	340,844

2.3 ARCTIC SOCIAL SCIENCES PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.3.1 Bering Sea Community Coordination

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	15,601	17,440	18,308	19,203	20,177	90,729
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	10,650	-	-	-	-	10,650
Materials and Supplies	60	-	-	-	-	60
Publications/Dissemination	10,000	-	-	-	-	10,000
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	2,600	-	-	-	-	2,600
Total direct costs	38,911	17,440	18,308	19,203	20,177	114,039
Total indirect costs	14,786	6,627	6,957	7,297	7,667	43,334
	53,697	24,067	25,265	26,500	27,844	157,373

2.3.2 Arctic Social Sciences Coordination

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	14,421	8,763	9,205	9,660	10,143	52,192
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	14,421	8,763	9,205	9,660	10,143	52,192
Total indirect costs	5,480	3,330	3,498	3,671	3,854	19,833
	19,901	12,093	12,703	13,331	13,997	72,025

Proposed Funding Detail by Project Activities

	<u>2006</u>	<u>2007</u>	<u>2008</u>	<u>2009</u>	<u>2010</u>	<u>Total</u>
2.4 ARCTIC SECTION SCIENCE MATERIALS						
2.4.1 <u>Arctic Section Science Materials</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	11,495	12,074	12,664	13,296	13,963	63,492
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	1,850	-	-	-	-	1,850
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	13,345	12,074	12,664	13,296	13,963	65,342
Total indirect costs	5,071	4,588	4,812	5,053	5,306	24,830
	18,416	16,662	17,476	18,349	19,269	90,172
Subtotal Direct Costs	484,842	475,574	368,664	374,056	368,701	2,071,837
Subtotal Indirect Costs	148,139	180,718	140,092	142,142	140,106	751,197
Total Arctic Sciences Section	632,981	656,292	508,756	516,198	508,807	2,823,034

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 <u>Arctic Science Education Activities</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	81,815	85,937	90,197	94,733	99,621	452,303
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,775	1,775	1,800	1,825	1,850	9,025
Participant Support Costs	19,525	19,525	19,800	20,075	20,350	99,275
Materials and Supplies	250	250	250	250	250	1,250
Publications/Dissemination	173	173	176	176	176	874
Consulting	11,500	11,500	11,500	11,500	11,500	57,500
Computer Services	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	16,875
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	50,000
Total direct costs	128,413	132,535	137,098	141,934	147,122	687,102
Total indirect cost	48,797	50,363	52,097	53,935	55,906	261,098
	177,210	182,898	189,195	195,869	203,028	948,200
3.2 <u>Arctic Visiting Speakers</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	11,669	14,899	15,635	16,377	17,237	75,817
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	29,625	29,625	30,000	30,375	30,750	150,375
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	41,294	44,524	45,635	46,752	47,987	226,192
Total indirect costs	15,692	16,919	17,341	17,766	18,235	85,953
	56,986	61,443	62,976	64,518	66,222	312,145
Subtotal Direct Costs	169,707	177,059	182,733	188,686	195,109	913,294
Subtotal Indirect Costs	64,489	67,282	69,438	71,701	74,141	347,051
Total Arctic Science Education	234,196	244,341	252,171	260,387	269,250	1,260,345

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 <u>Witness the Arctic Newsletters</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	70,380	74,378	78,078	81,926	86,026	390,788
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,775	1,775	1,800	1,825	1,850	9,025
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	100	100	100	100	100	500
Publications/Dissemination	40,200	24,700	40,200	40,200	24,700	170,000
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	112,455	100,953	120,178	124,051	112,676	570,313
Total indirect costs	42,733	38,362	45,668	47,139	42,817	216,719
	155,188	139,315	165,846	171,190	155,493	787,032
4.2 <u>Internet Resources</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	93,288	97,952	102,904	108,071	113,740	515,955
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	7,100	7,100	7,200	7,300	7,400	36,100
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	7,000	7,000	7,000	7,000	7,000	35,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	107,388	112,052	117,104	122,371	128,140	587,055
Total indirect costs	40,807	42,580	44,499	46,501	48,693	223,080
	148,195	154,632	161,603	168,872	176,833	810,135

Proposed Funding Detail by Project Activities

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Total
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	25,033	27,443	28,824	30,199	31,728	143,227
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	25,033	27,443	28,824	30,199	31,728	143,227
Total indirect costs	9,513	10,428	10,953	11,475	12,056	54,425
	34,546	37,871	39,777	41,674	43,784	197,652
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	23,543	28,842	30,375	31,795	33,435	147,990
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,775	1,775	1,800	1,825	1,850	9,025
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	1,000	1,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	25,318	30,617	32,175	33,620	36,285	158,015
Total indirect costs	9,621	11,634	12,227	12,776	13,788	60,046
	34,939	42,251	44,402	46,396	50,073	218,061
4.5 Internet Media Archive						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	46,727	49,106	51,518	53,985	56,733	258,069
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	1,775	-	-	-	-	1,775
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	10,000
Consulting	-	5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	20,000
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	48,502	56,606	59,018	61,485	64,233	289,844
Total indirect costs	18,431	21,510	22,427	23,364	24,408	110,140
	66,933	78,116	81,445	84,849	88,641	399,984
4.6 Arctic Research Broader Impacts Showcase						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	40,814	42,832	44,941	47,228	49,650	225,465
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	-	1,775	1,800	1,825	1,850	7,250
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and Supplies	-	-	-	-	-	-
Publications/Dissemination	-	-	-	-	-	-
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total direct costs	40,814	44,607	46,741	49,053	51,500	232,715
Total indirect costs	15,509	16,951	17,761	18,640	19,570	88,431
	56,323	61,558	64,502	67,693	71,070	321,146
4.7 Arctic Community Outreach						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	60,924	69,796	73,338	76,947	80,916	361,921
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)	17,750	17,750	18,000	7,300	7,400	68,200
Participant Support Costs	44,375	44,375	45,000	45,625	46,250	225,625
Materials and Supplies	250	250	250	250	250	1,250
Publications/Dissemination	7,894	7,894	7,900	7,900	7,900	39,488
Consulting	-	-	-	-	-	-
Computer Services	-	-	-	-	-	-
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	32,000	32,000	32,000	32,000	32,000	160,000
Total direct costs	163,193	172,065	176,488	170,022	174,716	856,484
Total indirect costs	62,013	65,384	67,065	64,609	66,392	325,463
	225,206	237,449	243,553	234,631	241,108	1,181,947
Subtotal Direct	522,703	544,343	580,528	590,801	599,278	2,837,653
Subtotal Indirect	198,627	206,849	220,600	224,504	227,724	1,078,304
Total Information and Outreach	721,330	751,192	801,128	815,305	827,002	3,915,957

Proposed Funding Detail by Project Activities

	<u>2006</u>	<u>2007</u>	<u>2008</u>	<u>2009</u>	<u>2010</u>	<u>Total</u>
5. CORE SUPPORT						
5.1 <u>Core Support</u>						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	109,593	146,746	154,015	161,860	170,042	742,256
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	22,188	22,188	22,500	22,813	23,125	112,814
Participant Support Costs	-	-	-	-	-	-
Materials and supplies	38,700	45,500	45,500	45,500	45,500	220,700
Publications/Dissemination	4,820	4,820	4,820	4,820	4,820	24,100
Consulting	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	50,000
Computer Services	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	3,375	16,875
Subawards	-	-	-	-	-	-
Other Direct Costs	10,325	14,050	14,050	14,050	14,050	66,525
Total direct costs	199,001	246,679	254,260	262,418	270,912	1,233,270
Total indirect costs	75,620	93,738	96,619	99,719	102,947	468,643
Total Core Support	274,621	340,417	350,879	362,137	373,859	1,701,913
Total Direct Costs all tasks	2,011,412	1,671,524	1,664,334	1,656,914	1,686,156	8,690,340
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	728,237	635,179	632,447	629,627	640,739	3,266,229
Total All Tasks	2,739,649	2,306,703	2,296,781	2,286,541	2,326,895	11,956,569
TOTAL						
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	963,699	1,003,288	1,052,838	1,105,090	1,161,664	5,286,579
Permanent Equipment	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel	94,963	86,088	83,700	64,788	61,975	391,514
Participant Support Costs	414,475	302,650	234,800	219,700	185,600	1,357,225
Materials and Supplies	47,380	47,250	46,850	46,750	46,550	234,780
Publications/Dissemination	77,670	41,898	56,796	56,636	64,417	297,417
Consulting	91,500	97,500	96,500	71,100	73,100	429,700
Computer Services	13,500	13,500	13,500	13,500	13,500	67,500
Subawards	95,000	-	-	-	-	95,000
Other Direct Costs	213,225	79,350	79,350	79,350	79,350	530,625
Total direct costs	2,011,412	1,671,524	1,664,334	1,656,914	1,686,156	8,690,340
Indirect Costs @ 38.0%	728,237	635,179	632,447	629,627	640,739	3,266,229
Total direct and indirect	<u>2,739,649</u>	<u>2,306,703</u>	<u>2,296,781</u>	<u>2,286,541</u>	<u>2,326,895</u>	<u>11,956,569</u>

Form 1030 Summary

<u>Form 1030 Category</u>		<u>5-year Budget</u>	<u>Year 1 Budget</u>	<u>Year 2 Budget</u>	<u>Year 3 Budget</u>	<u>Year 4 Budget</u>	<u>Year 5 Budget</u>
Salaries							
Executive director	A2	569,369	102,960	108,108	113,537	119,340	125,424
Other professionals	B2	2,672,416	485,294	507,588	532,739	559,208	587,587
Student	B3	74,585	13,475	14,175	14,875	15,610	16,450
Clerical	B5	514,477	96,603	97,148	101,774	106,630	112,322
Total salaries		3,830,847	698,332	727,019	762,925	800,788	841,783
Fringe Benefits							
Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	1,455,732	265,367	276,269	289,913	304,302	319,881
		5,286,579	963,699	1,003,288	1,052,838	1,105,090	1,161,664
Permanent Equipment							
	D	-	-	-	-	-	-
Travel (domestic)							
	E1	377,975	92,300	83,425	81,000	62,050	59,200
Travel (foreign)							
	E2	13,539	2,663	2,663	2,700	2,738	2,775
Total staff travel	E	391,514	94,963	86,088	83,700	64,788	61,975
Participant Support Costs							
Stipends	F1	40,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000
Travel	F2	675,850	206,100	149,400	116,550	110,200	93,600
Subsistence	F3	641,375	200,375	145,250	110,250	101,500	84,000
Total participant costs		1,357,225	414,475	302,650	234,800	219,700	185,600
Other Direct Costs							
Materials and supplies	G1	234,780	47,380	47,250	46,850	46,750	46,550
Publication cost/ docum/dissemin	G2	297,417	77,670	41,898	56,796	56,636	64,417
Consultant services	G3	429,700	91,500	97,500	96,500	71,100	73,100
Computer services	G4	67,500	13,500	13,500	13,500	13,500	13,500
Subawards	G5	95,000	95,000	-	-	-	-
Other	G6	530,625	213,225	79,350	79,350	79,350	79,350
Total other direct costs		1,655,022	538,275	279,498	292,996	267,336	276,917
Total direct costs	H	8,690,340	2,011,412	1,671,524	1,664,334	1,656,914	1,686,156
Indirect Costs (FY05 provisional 38%)							
	I	3,266,229	728,237	635,179	632,447	629,627	640,739
Total direct and indirect costs	J	11,956,569	2,739,649	2,306,703	2,296,781	2,286,541	2,326,895

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Cold Regions Laboratory Inc				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (1) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				4.00	0.00	0.00	21,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							21,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							7,980
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							28,980
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____							0
2. TRAVEL _____							0
3. SUBSISTENCE _____							0
4. OTHER _____							0
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							28,980
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0260, Base: 28980)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							11,020
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							40,000
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 40,000 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet		Initials - ORG

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Cold Regions Laboratory Inc				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.			
				Proposed	Granted		
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (0) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (1) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				4.00	0.00	0.00	21,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							21,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							7,980
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							28,980
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL							
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							0
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____				0			
2. TRAVEL _____				0			
3. SUBSISTENCE _____				0			
4. OTHER _____				0			
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)							
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							0
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							0
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							28,980
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							11,020
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							40,000
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 40,000 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked		Date Of Rate Sheet		Initials - ORG	

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION – Studies of the Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) Research Coordination
Cold Regions Research & Engineering Laboratory (CRREL)

Item B: Other Personnel

Line 2 –

Thomas A. Douglas will devote 362 hours @ \$58/hour as the SNACS Synthesis Facilitator (SSF), organizing and promoting synthesis between the six SNACS projects, and where applicable, between SNACS researchers and other groups working on coastal and/or arctic areas. In concert with the leadership of SNACS, the SSF will help the SNACS PIs agree on a synthesis goal, help to design a program to reach the goals and facilitate the process of producing synthesis products. Total budget for personnel costs is \$21,000.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

Fringe is budgeted at the current ARCUS rate of 38%. Total fringe benefits budgeted is \$7,980

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The indirect rate is estimated at 38.026% and totals \$11,020.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION University of Alaska Fairbanks Campus				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (1) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				2.00	0.00	0.00	17,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							17,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							6,500
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							23,500
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							3,500
2. FOREIGN							8,500
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____							0
2. TRAVEL _____							0
3. SUBSISTENCE _____							0
4. OTHER _____							0
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							1,788
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							1,788
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							37,288
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 47.5000, Base: 37288)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							17,712
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							55,000
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 55,000 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION University of Alaska Fairbanks Campus				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1.				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (0) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (1) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				2.00	0.00	0.00	17,000
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (0) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							0
5. (0) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							0
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							17,000
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							6,500
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							23,500
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL							3,500
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							3,500
2. FOREIGN							8,500
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS	\$		0				
2. TRAVEL			0				
3. SUBSISTENCE			0				
4. OTHER			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0)							
TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							0
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							0
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION							0
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES							0
4. COMPUTER SERVICES							0
5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							1,788
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							1,788
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							37,288
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							17,712
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							55,000
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 55,000 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet		Initials - ORG

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION – Center for Global Change, University of Alaska Fairbanks (HARC Core Office Support)

Item B: Other Personnel

Line 2 –

The University of Alaska Fairbanks continues to be committed to providing an institutional home to HARC through the provision of office space and faculty release time for Associate Professor of Anthropology, Maribeth S. Murray to continue as director in 2006/07. A one course teaching reduction will continue to function as UAF's contribution of Murray's paid time during each academic year to manage the Core Office. Nine additional weeks of support for Murray's time are sought through NSF and total \$17,000.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

Fringe is budgeted at 38% and totals \$6,500.

Item E: Travel

Travel, both domestic and foreign totals \$12,000 and will allow the Murray to continue participation at a national and international level in long-term collaborative Arctic research planning and capacity building efforts. Also included in this budget is a student travel award of \$2,500, an important step in building HARC research capacity and expanding the network of HD researchers interested in addressing ARCSS goals.

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Other direct costs totaling \$1,788 will cover conference calls and web meetings.

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The indirect rate is estimated at 47.5% and totals \$17,712.

Current and Pending Support

(See GPG Section II.C.2.h for guidance on information to include on this form.)

The following information should be provided for each investigator and other senior personnel. Failure to provide this information may delay consideration of this proposal.	
Investigator: Wendy Warnick	Other agencies (including NSF) to which this proposal has been/will be submitted.
Support: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program OPP-0101279	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Total Award Amount: \$ 9,668,638 Total Award Period Covered: 04/01/01 - 03/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 10.80 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Scoping Workshops: Planning, Facilitation, Coordination and Implementation for Vital Signs Monitoring in Alaska's Arctic National Parks	
Source of Support: National Park Service Total Award Amount: \$ 293,760 Total Award Period Covered: 10/01/04 - 06/30/06 Location of Project: Fairbanks Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.25 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Scoping Workshops: Planning, Facilitation, Coordination and Implementation for Vital Signs Monitoring in Alaska's Arctic National Parks	
Source of Support: National Park Service Total Award Amount: \$ 100,335 Total Award Period Covered: 01/01/05 - 12/31/06 Location of Project: Fairbanks Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.10 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Development of Phase 3 Report for the NPS Central Alaska Network	
Source of Support: National Park Service Total Award Amount: \$ 24,236 Total Award Period Covered: 09/21/04 - 1/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska and Woods Hole Research Center Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.10 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Collaborative Research: Developing and Implementing an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure to Support International Arctic Science	
Source of Support: NSF OPP - Arctic Research Support and Logistics Total Award Amount: \$ 999,915 Total Award Period Covered: 09/01/06 - 08/31/09 Location of Project: University of Redlands, ARCUS-Fairbanks, AK, UTEP Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 2.00 Acad: 0.00 Summ: 0.00	
*If this project has previously been funded by another agency, please list and furnish information for immediately preceding funding period.	

Current and Pending Support

(See GPG Section II.C.2.h for guidance on information to include on this form.)

The following information should be provided for each investigator and other senior personnel. Failure to provide this information may delay consideration of this proposal.	
Investigator: Wendy Warnick	Other agencies (including NSF) to which this proposal has been/will be submitted.
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: GeoSOAR - Geoscience Stories on Arctic Research	
Source of Support: NSF Geosciences Total Award Amount: \$ 148,624 Total Award Period Covered: 05/01/06 - 05/01/07 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska and Woods Hole Research Center Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.10 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Community Needs Assessment and Portal Prototype for an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (ASDI)	
Source of Support: NSF OPP - Arctic Research Support and Logistics Total Award Amount: \$ 177,593 Total Award Period Covered: 01/01/06 - 12/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.80 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: STUDENT-PARTNERS: A Pan-Arctic Science and Education Collaboration	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs Total Award Amount: \$ 613,401 Total Award Period Covered: 09/15/05 - 08/31/08 Location of Project: Woods Hole Research Center and ARCUS, Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.50 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program ARC-0101279: Supplement Request	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs Total Award Amount: \$ 1,188,044 Total Award Period Covered: 04/01/06 - 08/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 4.50 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program 2006-2011	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs Total Award Amount: \$ 11,956,563 Total Award Period Covered: 09/01/06 - 08/31/11 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 9.00 Acad: 0.00 Summ: 0.00	

*If this project has previously been funded by another agency, please list and furnish information for immediately preceding funding period.

Current and Pending Support

(See GPG Section II.C.2.h for guidance on information to include on this form.)

The following information should be provided for each investigator and other senior personnel. Failure to provide this information may delay consideration of this proposal.	
Investigator: Helen Wiggins	Other agencies (including NSF) to which this proposal has been/will be submitted.
Support: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program OPP-0101279	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs Total Award Amount: \$ 9,668,638 Total Award Period Covered: 04/01/01 - 03/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 12.00 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: GeoSOAR - Geoscience Stories on Arctic Research	
Source of Support: NSF - Geosciences Total Award Amount: \$ 148,624 Total Award Period Covered: 05/01/06 - 05/01/07 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 0.30 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Community Needs Assessment and Portal Prototype for an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure (ASDI)	
Source of Support: NSF OPP - Arctic Research Support and Logistics Total Award Amount: \$ 177,593 Total Award Period Covered: 01/01/06 - 12/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 1.75 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pending <input type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Collaborative Research: Developing and Implementing an Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure to Support International Arctic Science	
Source of Support: NSF OPP - Arctic Research Support and Logistics Total Award Amount: \$ 999,915 Total Award Period Covered: 09/01/06 - 08/31/09 Location of Project: University of Redlands, ARCUS-Fairbanks, AK, UTEP Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 3.40 Acad: 0.00 Sumr: 0.00	
Support: <input type="checkbox"/> Current <input type="checkbox"/> Pending <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Submission Planned in Near Future <input type="checkbox"/> *Transfer of Support Project/Proposal Title: Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program ARC-0101279: Supplement Request	
Source of Support: National Science Foundation Office of Polar Programs Total Award Amount: \$ 1,188,044 Total Award Period Covered: 04/01/06 - 08/31/06 Location of Project: ARCUS - Fairbanks, Alaska Person-Months Per Year Committed to the Project. Cal: 10.00 Acad: 0.00 Summ: 0.00	
*If this project has previously been funded by another agency, please list and furnish information for immediately preceding funding period.	

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT & OTHER RESOURCES

FACILITIES: Identify the facilities to be used at each performance site listed and, as appropriate, indicate their capacities, pertinent capabilities, relative proximity, and extent of availability to the project. Use "Other" to describe the facilities at any other performance sites listed and at sites for field studies. USE additional pages as necessary.

Laboratory:

Clinical:

Animal:

Computer: ARCUS is equipped with advanced communications and Internet capability with a secure operating environment for the servers and other computer equipment necessary to sustain the work proposed. ARCUS has its own server and T1 line and is equipped with the latest PC and Mac computer hardware

Office: The activities undertaken through this project will rely on the standard office facilities and equipment of ARCUS.

Other:

MAJOR EQUIPMENT: List the most important items available for this project and, as appropriate identifying the location and pertinent capabilities of each.

OTHER RESOURCES: Provide any information describing the other resources available for the project. Identify support services such as consultant, secretarial, machine shop, and electronics shop, and the extent to which they will be available for the project. Include an explanation of any consortium/contractual arrangements with other organizations.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT & OTHER RESOURCES

Continuation Page:

COMPUTER FACILITIES (continued):

and operating software and peripheral devices. Software programs and applications licensed and/or developed by ARCUS to support ARCUS programs and services, especially as regards community development activities, include relational database software, Microsoft Office, Adobe products, various browsers, website and server programs, listserv management, and online bulletin board and survey capabilities.

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